

Practices in Research

Demolition of Sopromer sardine canning factory chimney. Source: RaDdo.

Amphibious deconstructions

Sardines and demolished buildings

André Tavares, Alice Nouvet

Fishing Architecture ERC (ERC, Fish-A, 101044244)

Centro de Estudos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto

This is a historical survey. Although we are not designing projects to be built, we are using architectural tools to assess the extent to which the construction of fishing facilities has originated from or been dictated by marine ecosystems. Furthermore, architectural tools are capable of assisting the measurement of the impact these constructions have had on the marine environment. By representing the sardines' migrations, the movements and shifts in fishing activities, and the architectural typologies that are built to create an effective proximity between the industrial facilities and the sardines, we get a glimpse of how much the marine ecosystems and the built environment are entangled.

When looking at the deconstructions of the canning factories, a recurring theme is to correlate the ups and downs of the sardine industry with fluctuations in the sardine populations at sea: when sardines disappear from the coast, the sardine industry suffers. But such an equivalence leaves little room for understanding the symbiotic complexity between decaying buildings and sardines. The perception of sardine populations is limited by the epistemologies of the humans that assess and relate to them, be it fishermen or scientists. The transparent waters or the ocean are opaque to our knowledge, and only a small fraction of sardine behaviors can be grasped. It seems sardines keep their habits to themselves, a wise strategy considering what voracious predators humans can be. The result is an asymmetrical perception between land and sea.

3494. DOUARNENEZ — Les Plomarc'hs

Collection VILLARD, Quimper

Maintenance of sardines fishing boats. Source: Archives Départementales du Finistère.

It is in this asymmetry, in this voluntary distance kept by sardines, that architectural research can be inscribed, between construction and ecosystems. Prior historical research on sardines has focused on the catastrophes that vanishing fish have inflicted on the built environment. Architects follow that pattern, blaming the sardines' absence on the decayed constructions. But what does a sardine say? In other words, can architectural tools be used to render the arguments of sardines? Could their deconstructions and their material histories tell us something about sardines and their disappearance? To what extent can the architectural tools that are commonly employed to describe the built environment be adapted and used to assess complex ecosystems? Can architectural practice bring us closer to other species?

Fishing Architecture is a research project funded by the European Union (ERC, Fish-A, 101044244).

PRACTICES IN RESEARCH

Packing sardines. Source: Archives Départementales du Finistère.

Extension of the Sardine Canning Factory Amieux: Archives Municipales de Nantes.